

Synthesis of 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene.

BY S. KRISHNA AND RADHA KRISHNA.

While studying the therapeutic value of azo-dyestuffs, Ehrlich found that the compounds containing amino- and hydroxyl-groups in the *ortho*-position were the most active in destroying trypanosomes. (Ehrlich and Hata, "Experimental Chemotherapy in Spirillooses," 1911, p. 18). With this object in view he prepared, the now famous salvarsan for treatment of diseases of the syphilitic origin, but found that there was one serious objection to the use of salvarsan in that it got readily oxidised into a highly poisonous substance and that its aqueous solutions were distinctly acidic and had to be exactly neutralised with alkali just before intravenous injection. Accordingly, Lucius and Bruning (D.R.-P. 245756) prepared neo-salvarsan, a soluble salt free from the above drawback.

A large number of organo-metallic compounds of arsenic are known but no attempts have so far been made to prepare the thiol-analogues of salvarsan or neosalvarsan. The only effort in this direction was made by Hewitt, King and Murch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1359) who unsuccessfully attempted to prepare such compounds. The present work describes the preparation of certain arsenic compounds containing thiol-residues in the ring. These compounds contain tervalent arsenic and the preparation was undertaken with the hope that the presence of sulphur in the benzene nucleus might probably increase their trypanocidal value.

Our first attempt to prepare thiol-compounds was from potassium benzene sulphonate, which on being arsenated by Bechamp's method (*Compt. rend.*, 1863, 56, 1172) was expected to react in the following manner:—

did not proceed, while at the temperature of boiling water the xanthate decomposed. It was found that maximum coupling took place at 50—60°. The conversion of (V) into (VI) is probably in accordance with Lieb's experiments (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 1511) who converted *p*-phenylene diarsenic acid $\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2$ into

by heating the former at 50-60° for sometime.

The constitution of the thiolarsenobenzene, in all probability, is as shown in (VI) and this view has been further confirmed by preparing and studying some of its derivatives. It was found that cold hydriodic acid has no action on the compound but when heated with the acid and phosphorus it decomposed, one of the products being thiophenol. Similar results were obtained when thiolarsenide was heated for about eight hours with hydriodic acid under pressure at 120-130°. Oxidising agents, such as chlorine or dilute nitric acid, convert (VI) into the sulphonic acid, $\text{SO}_3\text{H} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{As} \cdot \text{O}(\text{OH})_2$, a substance soluble in water, and an insoluble diarsenic acid disulphide (IV) (Hewitt, King and Murch, *loc cit.*).

A number of additive compounds of 4:4'-dithiolarsenobenzene (VI) have been prepared and these, in all probability, possess the constitution of the type $\text{R} \cdot \text{As} = \text{As} \cdot \text{R} \dots \text{A}$ and $\text{R} \cdot \text{As} = \text{As} \cdot \text{R} \dots 2\text{A}$, where A stands for the compound attached. These are in confirmation with the theory of residual affinity in case of one or both of arsenic atoms. It is well known that arsenobenzene and its derivatives form additive compounds of the type $\text{R} \cdot \text{As} = \text{As} \cdot \text{R} \dots \text{MeX}$ and $\text{R} \cdot \text{As} = \text{As} \cdot \text{R} \dots 2\text{MeX}$, and the formation is presumably due to the residual affinity of one or both arsenic atoms, as arsenobenzene itself which contains neither the hydroxy- nor amino-groups can form such derivatives (Ehrlich, *Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 1634). It has been found that 4:4'-dithiolarsenobenzene (VI) combines with three molecules of acetyl chloride to give $[\text{AcS} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{As} = \text{As} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{SAC}] \dots \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{COCl}$ (VII), two molecules of acetyl chloride reacting with the thiol-group and a third molecule attaching itself to form an additive compound. With

thionyl chloride a slightly different type of compound namely (VIII) is formed.

The above constitution is very probable for this compound, since on treatment with water the compound (IX) is formed. With picric acid, perchloric acid, methyl iodide, dimethyl sulphate, hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid, the reaction proceeds in the normal manner giving compounds of the type $\text{R}\cdot\text{As}=\text{As}\cdot\text{R}\dots 2\text{A}$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene (VI).—*p*-Arsanilic acid (20 g.) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (25 c.c. diluted with 50 c.c. water) and cooled to 0°. Sodium nitrite (10 g.) dissolved in water (40 c.c.) was slowly added to the above mixture, without letting the temperature rise above 5°. The diazo-solution thus obtained was slowly added to a solution of potassium ethylxanthate (14 g.) in alkali (12 g. KOH in 30 c.c. of water) at 55-60° when a vigorous reaction took place and the colour of the solution changed from yellow to red. On evaporation of the solution, the residue was dissolved in water (100 c.c.) and acidified with hydrochloric acid when a colourless precipitate separated which turned yellow on standing. It is insoluble in most organic solvents except pyridine from which it was obtained in micro-crystalline prisms (yield, 75%). For purification, it was dissolved in dilute alkali and carefully precipitated with acids, the operation being repeated a number of times. The substance did not melt but decomposed above 280°. (Found: C, 38.70; H, 3.61; As, 40.32; S, 17.84. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{S}_2\text{As}_2$ requires C, 39.13; H, 2.71; As, 40.76; S, 17.39 per cent.).

The *disodium* salt is obtained by dissolving the thiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) in sodium hydroxide (10 c.c. of 5%) solution. On boiling with animal charcoal a yellow solution was obtained which was evaporated slowly in a desiccator and the residue crystallised from alcohol in yellow plates, highly soluble in water. (Found: Na, 11.30. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{S}_2\text{Na}_2\text{As}_2$ requires Na, 11.16 per cent.).

The *potassium* salt is prepared in a similar manner.

Isolation of p-Xanthyldiazobenzene Arsenic Acid (V).

p-Arsanilic acid (2 g.) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) and diazotised in the usual manner with sodium nitrite (0.8 g.) dissolved in water (4 c.c.). The diazotised solution was next added to potassium ethylxanthate (1.5 g.) dissolved in potassium hydroxide (2 c.c. of 50 %) solution. A yellow crystalline powder (K-salt) separated which was quickly removed, washed with alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. (Found: As, 17.00. $C_9H_9O_4N_2S_2K_2As$ requires As, 17.60 per cent.).

Diacetyl-4:4'-dithiolarsenobenzene Acetyl Chloride (VII).

To acetyl chloride (7 g.) the thiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) was added in small portions, when a vigorous action took place. The reaction was completed by heating the solution on a water-bath for half an hour and the cooled solution was poured into ice-cold water. A white solid separated which was crystallised from pyridine in colourless micro-prisms (yield, theoretical). It does not melt. (Found: As, 28.40; Cl, 6.58. $C_{18}H_{17}O_3ClS_2As_2$ requires As, 28.27; Cl, 6.6 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene and Thionyl Chloride: Formation of (IX).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) was gradually added to thionyl chloride (5 c.c.). To complete the reaction the solution was heated on a water-bath for half an hour and then the cooled mixture was poured in cold water. A white solid separated out, which was filtered, dried and crystallised from alcoholic pyridine in small prismatic needles. The substance does not melt and becomes semi-solid and brown on standing in air. (Found: As, 25.80; Cl, 5.91. $C_{12}H_{11}O_6ClS_5As_2$ requires As, 25.14; Cl, 5.96 per cent.).

The sodium salt is easily prepared by dissolving the substance (1 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c. of 10 %). The residue obtained on drying the solution was crystallised from alcohol in colourless micro-crystalline powder. (Found: Na, 10.78. $C_{12}H_8O_6ClS_5Na_3As_2$ requires Na, 10.41 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene Ethyl Chlorocarbonate, (SH·C₆H₄·As)₂...Cl·CO₂Et.

The thiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) and ethyl chlorocarbonate (5 g.) were suspended in alcohol and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. The

solution was filtered and poured into ice-cold water. A white solid separated which was filtered, dried and crystallised from alcohol in colourless micro-crystalline powder. The substance does not melt. (Found. As, 31.71; Cl, 6.88. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2ClS_2As_2$ requires As, 31.48; Cl, 7.45 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene Picrate, $(SH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot As)_2 \dots 2C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$.—Equal quantities of the thiolarsenobenzene and picric acid in alcohol were carefully heated on a water-bath for a short time and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. On treatment with acids a brown precipitate was obtained from the filtered solution from which the excess of picric acid was removed on boiling with alcohol, and the brown residue left behind was crystallised from pyridine in light brown micro-crystalline powder. It does not melt. (Found: As, 18.24. $C_{74}H_{16}O_{14}N_6S_2As$ requires As, 18.15 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene Perchlorate, $(SH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot As)_2 \dots 2HClO_4$.

Perchloric acid (5 g.) was added to the thiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution and the mixture heated on a water-bath for an hour. On cooling, the mixture was acidified, when a white crystalline mass separated, the purification of which was effected by repeated precipitation from its alkaline solutions by acid. It is a colourless micro-crystalline powder, insoluble in all the organic solvents and has no melting point. (Found: As, 26.25; Cl, 11.70. $C_{12}H_{12}O_8Cl_2S_2As_2$ requires As, 26.36; Cl, 12.47 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene Methiodide, $(HS \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot As)_2 \dots 2CH_3I$.

To an alkaline solution of the thiolarsenobenzene, methyl iodide was added at 40°. A vigorous reaction took place which was completed by warming on a water-bath. The solution on treatment with hydrochloric acid gave a yellow precipitate, which on drying was crystallised from alcohol in yellow micro-needles, which did not melt. (Found: As, 23.85; S, 9.29. $C_{14}H_{16}I_2S_2As_2$ requires As, 23.00; S, 9.81 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiomethylarsenobenzene Dimethylsulphate, $(CH_3S \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot As)_2 \dots 2(CH_3)_2SO_4$.

Dimethyl sulphate was slowly added to an alkaline solution of the thiolarsenobenzene. A vigorous reaction took place with evolution of heat. The solution was then heated on a water-bath, for about half an hour and on acidifying the cooled solution, a white precipitate

was thrown down which was collected, dried and crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles which do not melt. (Found: As, 22.7. $C_{18}H_{26}O_8S_2As_2$ requires As, 23.14 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene Hydrochloride, $(SH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot As)_2 \dots 2HCl$.

The thiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) was suspended in concentrated hydrochloric acid and kept warm for several hours. It was then diluted with water and the white precipitate obtained was well washed. (Found: As, 34.73. $C_{12}H_{12}Cl_2S_2As_2$ requires As, 34.01 per cent.).

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene Hydrogen Sulphate, $(HS \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot As)_2 \dots 2H_2SO_4$.

To a concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) the thiolarsenobenzene (2 g.) was gradually added with constant stirring. The mixture was then warmed to 50° for 2 hours, cooled and poured over ice. A white solid separated which was thoroughly washed with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It is a colourless crystalline powder having no melting point. (Found: As, 27.18. $C_{12}H_{14}O_8S_4As_2$ requires As, 26.59 per cent.).

Action of Oxidising Agents on 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene.

(a) *Chlorine.* 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene suspended in alcohol was saturated with dry chlorine gas when the suspended matter dissolved. The solution was then filtered, boiled with animal charcoal, evaporated to dryness and the residue was crystallised from absolute alcohol in colourless micro-crystalline powder, highly soluble in water. This substance is in all probability 1-sulpho-4-phenylarsinic acid, $SO_3H \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot AsO(OH)_2$. (Found: S 11.43. $C_6H_7O_6SAs$ requires S, 11.34 per cent.).

(b) *Nitric acid.* 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene was heated with 30 per cent. nitric acid on a water-bath. On pouring the solution in water a light yellow precipitate was obtained, which was collected, washed and dried. The solid was found to consist of two substances one of which is soluble and the other completely insoluble in all the organic solvents.

The insoluble portion was purified by precipitating its alkaline solution with acids. Its reactions indicate that it is diphenyl disulphide 4:4'-diarsinic acid. (Found: S, 14.00. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6S_2As_2$ requires

S, 13.73 per cent.). The disulphide is slightly soluble in dilute nitric acid from which it may be crystallised in needles.

The *soluble* portion was crystallised from alcohol in colourless micro-crystalline plates. It is probably a *p*-sulphophenyl arsenic acid, $\text{SO}_3\text{H}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{As}\cdot\text{O}(\text{OH})_2$. (Found: S, 11.28. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{O}_6\text{SAs}$ requires S, 11.34 per cent.). A further quantity of the sulpho-acid was obtained from the nitric acid mother-liquors on evaporation to a syrup with repeated addition of water to remove excess of acid. On careful evaporation in a desiccator, a crystalline mass was obtained, which was redissolved in water and crystallised by leaving a concentrated solution in a desiccator.

(c) *Hydrogen Peroxide*. 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene was heated with hydrogen peroxide in an alkaline medium, on a water-bath for 4 hours. On making the solution acid a yellow precipitate was obtained which was collected and further purified by repeatedly dissolving in alkali and precipitating with acid. In this way a yellow micro-crystalline powder having the formula, $\text{SH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{As}\cdot\text{O}(\text{OH})_2$ was formed. It does not melt but decomposes on heating above 250° . (Found. S, 13.41. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{SAs}$ requires S, 13.67 per cent.).

Action of Hydriodic Acid.—4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene decomposes into thiophenol and arsenic acid when heated with hydriodic acid. A similar behaviour was observed when the substance was heated with hydriodic acid under pressure at $120-130^\circ$. Hydriodic acid was found to have no action at all on the substance in the cold.

Summary.

4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene has been prepared by coupling diazotised *p*-arsanilic acid with potassium ethylxanthate and hydrolysing the product. Analytical work shows it to have the formula, $\text{SH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{As}=\text{As}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SH}$ and this has been further confirmed by a study of its derivatives. 4:4'-Dithiolarsenobenzene has characteristic mercaptanic properties and forms additive compounds of the type $(\text{SH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{As})_2 \dots \text{A}$ with acetyl chloride, thionyl chloride and ethyl chlorocarbonate. With hydrochloric acid, methyl iodide, dimethyl sulphate, picric acid, perchloric acid, etc., compounds of the type $(\text{SH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{As})_2 \dots \text{2A}$ are formed. Reducing agents have practically no effect, while oxidising agents convert it into a disulphide $[\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{S}]_2$ and a sulpho-acid $\text{SO}_3\text{H}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2$.